

A computational model for prediction of clot platelet content in flow-diverted intracranial aneurysms

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Abstract

Treatment of intracranial aneurysms with flow-diverting stents is a safe and minimally invasive technique. The goal is stable embolisation that facilitates stent endothelialisation, and elimination of the aneurysm. However, it is not fully understood why some aneurysms fail to develop a stable clot even with sufficient levels of flow reduction. Computational prediction of thrombus formation dynamics can help predict the post-operative response in such challenging cases. In this work, we propose a new model of thrombus formation and platelet dynamics inside intracranial aneurysms. Our novel contribution combines platelet activation and transport with fibrin generation, which is key to characterising stable and unstable thrombus. The model is based on two types of thrombus inside aneurysms: red thrombus (fibrin- and erythrocyte-rich) can be found in unstable clots, while white thrombus (fibrin- and platelet-rich) can be found in stable clots. The thrombus generation model is coupled to a CFD model and the flow-induced platelet index (FiPi) is defined as a quantitative measure of clot stability. Our model is validated against an in-vitro phantom study of two flow-diverting stents with different sizing. We demonstrate that our model accurately predicts the lower thrombus stability in the oversized stent scenario. This opens possibilities for using computational simulations to improve endovascular treatment planning and reduce adverse events, such as delayed haemorrhage of flow-diverted aneurysms.

Keywords: Flow diverter, Intracranial aneurysms, Thrombosis, Computational fluid dynamics

1. Introduction

1 Treatment of large and wide-necked intracranial aneurysms of the anterior circulation with
2 flow-diverting stents is safe and effective [5, 7, 11]. However, post-treatment rupture after
3 seemingly successful treatment, reported in almost 2% of cases [7, 20], is associated with high
4 risks of mortality and morbidity. There is a growing consensus that assessment of thrombus
5 composition must successfully predict flow diverter (FD) performance [9, 11, 19, 20, 21, 36, 41].
6 Two types of thrombi have been identified from autopsy studies of aneurysms: white thrombus,
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rich in fibrin and platelets [11, 36], and red thrombus. Red thrombus is characterised by: (i) less enmeshed platelets [11, 36], (ii) not facilitating the formation of a neointimal layer [17, 33], (iii) being prone to continuous fibrinolysis and renewal [36, 37, 39], and (iv) inducing autolytic activities in the wall resulting in weakening of the wall and ultimately rupture [11, 19, 36]. Non-organised red thrombi after flow diversion has been suggested as a potential predictor for post-treatment rupture [9, 21, 11, 19, 20, 36].

While the mechanisms of FD-induced thrombosis are not well understood, there is a consensus that blood flow stasis induced by flow diversion is the dominant driver of the clot formation in intracranial aneurysms. The clots found in flow-diverted aneurysms are closer in structure to those clots formed under stagnant flow in venous thrombosis rather than those formed in high shear-induced arterial thrombosis [19, 29, 34, 40]. In flow stasis, secretion of tissue factor by endothelium [6], white blood cells [6], and hypoxic platelets [6, 38]; and, secretion of platelet activating factors by endothelium [10] and hypoxic red blood cells [6, 1, 32] are associated with fibrin generation and platelet activation, the two major components of clot formation. Regions with low shear flow and high residence time promote platelet activation and adhesion [10, 27], and stabilisation of platelet aggregates [24]. They also enhance platelet-fibrin and platelet-endothelium interactions [27]. It has been hypothesised that platelets can be activated in high-shear regions near the FD struts or because of blood contact with the FD wires [15, 35]. Such effects are avoided by dual antiplatelet therapies [15, 34, 35] or modification/coating of the wires [13, 14, 22] to minimise the risk of thromboembolic events distal to the aneurysm [15, 34, 35]. Hence, despite a diverse set of initiation mechanisms, flow stasis can be the nexus between them all. In our proposed model we focus on flow stasis as the pathway to thrombus formation.

While extensive computational investigations have focused on modelling thrombosis in flow systems, few studies have simulated coupled haemodynamics and biochemistry in flow-diverted aneurysms [25, 26]. Taking thrombin concentration as a surrogate for thrombosis, Ngoepe et al. [25] simulated clot growth in aneurysms after flow diversion, and an assumption was made that thrombin generation originated on the endothelial wall due to tissue damage. Ou et al. [26] focused on stasis-induced expression on blood-borne tissue factor as the initiator and simulated fibrin generation inside the flow-diverted aneurysm. Although these studies presented promising results on simulation-based prediction of FD-induced thrombosis, they did not predict the platelet composition of the clot or its stability. Our model is the first to attempt computational thrombus stability analysis in realistic three-dimensional aneurysms after flow-diversion.

The objective of this study is to create a coupled flow and thrombosis model capable of predicting the stability of the clot that forms after flow diversion. A computational thrombosis model must consider estimation of the clot extent and stability in terms of composition of its structural components, i.e. fibrin and platelets. We consider FD-induced stasis as a surrogate for all the above mentioned thrombosis initiation mechanisms and simultaneously model thrombin and fibrin generation, and platelet activation and aggregation in stagnation regions. We validate our model against an in-vitro experiment performed in [12], in which thrombus formation was examined in an aneurysm phantom treated with FD's of different sizes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Model of thrombosis after flow diversion

Our model is based on bulk initiation and propagation of thrombosis due to flow stasis. Increased flow residence time, decreased flow velocity, decreased shear rate, and decreased vorticity have been used to characterise flow stasis in aneurysms [8, 28, 30]. When compared with

Figure 1: Left panel: schematic representation of platelet transport to the clotting site. Right panel: schematic representation of the clotting reaction network modelled in this study.

54 thrombosed regions, velocity, vorticity, and shear rate were reported to be 2.8 times larger in
 55 non-thrombosed regions of elastase-induced aneurysms in animal models [8]. Based on a har-
 56 monic analysis of shear rate waves in ten aneurysms, de Sousa *et al.* [10] determined 25 s^{-1} as
 57 the threshold for thrombosis. Rayz *et al.* [30] showed that thrombus deposits in aneurysmal
 58 regions with a residence time greater than $18.22 \pm 11 \text{ s}$. We therefore assumed thrombosis to
 59 initiate and progress in *prothrombotic* regions of the aneurysm after flow diversion, i.e., regions
 60 with time-averaged shear rate smaller than $\text{SR}_t = 25 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [10] and residence time greater than
 61 $\text{RT}_t = 5 \text{ s}$ [30].

62 We considered four biochemically-coupled events that result in a clot of fibrin mesh and
 63 aggregated platelets: (i) *Thrombin generation* occurs by conversion of prothrombin to throm-
 64 bin on the surface of resting and activated platelets, where the reaction kinetics are faster for
 65 activated platelets. Also considered is thrombin inhibition by its primary plasma inhibitor (anti-
 66 thrombin), in the absence of heparin catalysis. (ii) *Fibrin generation* occurs in the presence of
 67 thrombin, which converts fibrinogen to fibrin monomers. We did not consider further polymeri-
 68 sation of the fibrin monomers. (iii) *Platelet activation* occurs when resting platelets become
 69 activated by exposure to thrombin or other activated platelets. The latter mechanism was a
 70 surrogate for activation by agonists released from other activated platelets [18]. (iv) *Platelet*
 71 *aggregation* in the presence of fibrin takes place when platelets attached to the fibrin network
 72 aggregate to form bound platelets. Bound platelets were assumed to activate prothrombin and
 73 other resting platelets. Our model included five biochemical species: prothrombin (PT), throm-
 74 bin (TH), anti-thrombin (AT), fibrinogen (FG), fibrin (FI). Three categories of platelets; resting
 75 platelets (RP), activated platelets (AP), and fibrin bound aggregated platelets (BP) were con-
 76 sidered. A schematic representation of the biochemical species and reactions is given in Figure
 77 1. Mathematical description of our thrombosis model and the governing equations are provided
 78 in the Supplementary Material.

79 2.2. Flow induced Platelet index (FiPi)

80 We defined the *flow induced platelet index* (FiPi) as the relative difference of the platelet
 81 concentration between a closed and an open system:

$$82 \mathcal{P} = \frac{C_{bp}^{open} - C_{bp}^{closed}}{C_{bp}^{closed}} = \frac{C_{bp}^{open}}{C_{rp,0} + C_{ap,0}} - 1. \quad (1)$$

83 In equation (1), $C_{rp,0}$ and $C_{ap,0}$ are initial concentrations of resting and activated platelets
 in the clot-free blood, respectively. FiPi quantifies the effect of blood flow on transport of

Figure 2: The first two columns represent the concept of the flow-induced platelet index (FiPi). In a closed system, the platelet content of the clot is equal to the initial concentration of platelets in the container before clotting occurred. In an open system, more platelets are advected with the blood flow to the clotting site, where they can attach to the clot and increase the clot platelet content. The third column shows the phantom from [12] (first row) and the computer models of the phantom (before and after FD placement) used in this study.

84 platelets to and from the site of clot formation and consequently on the final platelet content
 85 of the formed clot. As shown in Figure 2, in a closed system with no inflow or outflow, we
 86 assumed the concentration of bound platelets in a formed clot to be equal to the summation of
 87 the concentrations of resting and activated platelets at the initial state before any clot formed.
 88 However, in an open system, where blood can flow over and through the forming clot, the final
 89 concentration of bound platelets in the formed clot would differ from that in closed systems. In
 90 flow-diverted aneurysms, it has been hypothesised that the flow entering the sac brings platelets
 91 into contact with the forming clot and promotes formation of a higher platelet content clot [41].

92 2.3. Computational model validation

93 Gester et al. [12] evaluated intra-aneurysmal FD-induced thrombus formation. Two FD's
 94 of same type with two diameters were deployed in a silicone phantom of a simplified lateral
 95 aneurysm; one of the FD's had a diameter of 4.00 mm (FD-4.0) the other was oversized with a
 96 diameter of 4.50 mm (FD-4.5). The phantom aneurysm was spherical with an inner diameter
 97 of 6.4 mm and a neck width of 6.0 mm. The tubular parent vessel had an inner diameter
 98 of 4.2 mm with an angle of 120° at the aneurysm neck. Blood from the cervical artery of
 99 slaughter house pigs were circulated in the phantom model. Particle imaging velocimetry (PIV)
 100 and Doppler sonography were performed to monitor the flow inside aneurysm. The FD-induced
 101 intra-aneurysmal clots were qualitatively evaluated once the sonography signal no longer existed
 102 (i.e., 10-12 hours after the experiments started). In the aneurysm treated with FD-4.0, a red
 103 cap-shaped clot was observed, mostly consisting of organised and platelet-rich clot formed with
 104 a growth direction opposite to the entering flow jet. In the aneurysm treated with the oversized
 105 stent, FD-4.5, a less platelet-rich clot filling almost the entire sac with no clear growth direction
 106 was observed with only a rigid (platelet-rich) region near the center of the aneurysm. We built
 107 computer models of the phantom experiments and compared computational simulations of the
 108 FD-induced thrombosis against in-vitro observations reported in [12]. Details on the computer
 109 models and the numerical simulations are presented in the Supplementary Material.

Table 1: Haemodynamic quantifications before and immediately after FD placement, averaged over time and the sac. Values in parentheses indicate changes from the pre-FD quantity.

	Velocity [m/s]	Residence time [s]	Shear rate [s ⁻¹]
Before FD placement	0.043	0.649	89.66
After FD placement			
FD-4.0	0.003(-93%)	7.504(+1,056%)	5.786(-94%)
FD-4.5	0.008(-81%)	1.947(+200%)	18.59(-79%)

110 3. Results

111 3.1. Aneurysmal haemodynamics before/after flow diversion

112 Table 1 shows pre- and post-treatment haemodynamic quantifications based on the the flow
113 simulations before the thrombosis was activated (the first set of simulations). Both FD configura-
114 tions induced flow stasis in the aneurysm sac. Figure 3 shows intra-aneurysmal haemodynamics
115 along the aneurysm sagittal mid-plane before and immediately after FD deployment before any
116 clot formed. To enable a qualitative comparison with the PIV measurements made in [12], we
117 ran pulsatile flow simulations, with no chemical reaction, and presented velocity contour plots
118 at the peak systole. In Figure 3, shear rate and residence time contour plots are taken from
119 steady-state simulations and represent the time-averaged values.

120 3.2. Thrombus formation and comparison to in-vitro observations

121 The thrombosis initiation criteria ($SR < 25 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $RT > 5 \text{ s}$) were not met in the simu-
122 lations of intra-aneurysmal flow before FD placement, therefore, as expected, no clot formed
123 in the aneurysm sac. According to previous studies [2, 3], we assumed the clot to be formed
124 in regions where the fibrin concentration is greater than 600 nM. In Figure 4 (first row), the
125 white iso-lines, drawn at fibrin concentrations of 600 nM, show the thrombus front. The dark
126 red is associated with fibrin concentrations greater than 3500 nM, showing an almost complete
127 conversion of plasma fibrinogen into fibrin. In agreement with [12], both FD's developed a clot
128 that filled nearly the entire sac. In the FD-4.0 case, more pronounced formation and anchorage
129 of fibrin strands to the proximal region of the FD were reported in the phantom experiments
130 once the clot began to form. A proximal-to-distal direction of clot growth was reported in the
131 FD-4.0 case, as opposed to no clear growth direction in the case treated with FD-4.5. Based on
132 the transient results (see fibrin concentration contour plots at $t = 10 \text{ s}$ in Figure 4), we observed
133 that in the aneurysm treated with FD-4.0, the clot formed from the aneurysm proximal region
134 and grew in a direction opposite to the entering flow jet direction to fill the aneurysm. In the
135 aneurysm treated with FD-4.5, there was also a clot forming in the central part of the aneurysm
136 (the central recirculation zone), growing with no preferred direction. We also observed a thicker
137 band of high fibrin concentration started from the proximal region of FD and extended across
138 the sac to the upper distal wall.

139 Figure 4 (second row) shows contour plots of FiPi used to measure the effect of blood flow
140 on the clot platelet content. In the FD-4.0 case, our results showed a platelet-rich clot (FiPi >
141 0.15) covering the entire aneurysm neck and extended towards the upper wall. However, in the
142 FD-4.5 case, formation of the platelet-rich clot was limited to the central region of the sac. We
143 observed a less platelet-rich clot at the proximal region of the aneurysm (in both cases) and in a
144 small region at the centre of the platelet-rich clot formed in the centre of the aneurysm treated

Figure 3: Intra-aneurysmal haemodynamic quantification before and immediately after FD deployment. Velocity quantifications were made at the peak systole to enable comparisons with PIV measurements made in [12]. Flow direction is indicated with black arrows on the left column and is the same in other columns.

145 with the oversized FD. This observation agrees with [12], where a clot with a generally higher
 146 platelet content was reportedly induced by the FD-4.0, and regions with high platelet content
 147 around the central vortex were reported in the FD-4.5 case.

148 4. Discussion

149 4.1. Thrombus formation and model validation

150 The in-vitro study [12] compared the effects of flow diversion by two stents in the same
 151 silicone phantom. In both cases, the phantom was filled with thrombus at the end of the ex-
 152 periment, at which point the authors removed the silicone model and provided snapshots of the
 153 induced clots. To enable comparisons with [12], we set a threshold on FiPi, the measure of
 154 platelet content, and extracted from this the platelet-rich clot morphology. The morphology of
 155 the clots obtained from our model showed the best qualitative agreement with snapshots of the
 156 phantom experiment, when we used $\text{FiPi} > 0.15$ as a threshold. Figure 4, the third row, shows
 157 our model predictions of the morphology of the platelet-rich clot and snapshots of the phantoms
 158 taken from [12]. While we emphasise that $\text{FiPi} > 0.15$ is not a generalised threshold, we explored
 159 what happens to the morphology of the platelet-rich clots when we set a different threshold on
 160 FiPi. We examined thresholds $\text{FiPi} > 0.10$ and $\text{FiPi} > 0.20$. We used the Dice similarity co-
 161 efficient (DSC) to compare the volumetric overlap between the morphologies produced by the
 162 new thresholds and the reference morphology extracted from $\text{FiPi} > 0.15$. High DSC scores

Figure 4: Simulation of thrombosis in flow diverted aneurysms. In the first two rows, fibrin concentration contour plots are presented on the aneurysm sagittal mid-plane. In the first row, the white solid line represents a concentration of 600 nM. In the third row, for each flow-diverter, model predictions of the high-platelet content clot morphology (left) are compared against snapshots of the clots (right) from in-vitro observations reported in [12]. The snapshots and the model predictions are presented in the same spatial scale and dotted lines are used to show the clot extent above the FDs. Flow direction is indicated with black arrows on the left column and is the same in other columns.

163 92.0% and 92.9% were achieved when the morphologies extracted from $\text{FiPi} > 0.10$ and FiPi
 164 > 0.20 thresholds was compared to the reference morphology, respectively. This demonstrates
 165 that thresholding FiPi is a robust way to predict.

166

167 *Location of the clot and the growth direction.* In both cases, in-vitro experiments [12] showed
 168 that the clot started to form on the proximal wall. With FD-4.5, the course of thrombosis con-
 169 tinued by formation of fibrin as a result of stagnation of blood at the centre sac, i.e., the central
 170 vortex. Fibrin then filled the aneurysm without a clear growth direction. With FD-4.0, the
 171 clot grew layer-by-layer and filled the aneurysm towards the distal wall. Our thrombosis model
 172 correctly predicted the locations of clot deposition and the growth directions reported in these
 173 in-vitro experiments. Cebal et al. [8] reported a layer-wise growth of clot from regions with
 174 smaller velocity, shear rates, and vorticity, i.e., the dome, towards the flow-diverted aneurysm
 175 neck. These results show that the thresholds we found based on residence time and shear rate
 176 were valid and that our model predicted realistic thrombi deposition location and growth direc-
 177 tion.

178

179 *Location of the high platelet content clot.* In the FD-4.0 case, simulations indicated a transfor-
 180 mation from inertia-driven to shear-driven flow (Figure 3). Flow stasis along the proximal wall

181 resulted in rapid formation of a less platelet-rich clot. However, during the course of thrombo-
182 sis, the shear-driven, well-distributed blood flow promoted the attachment of platelets to the
183 forming clot. This finally helped to form a homogeneous platelet-rich clot almost in the entire
184 aneurysm. However in the aneurysm treated with the oversized stent FD-4.5, inertial effects
185 persisted in the post-treatment flow and circulation in the aneurysm sac was observed (Fig-
186 ure 3). Although less pronounced than in the FD-4.0, extensive stasis along the proximal wall
187 resulted in the rapid formation of a less platelet-rich clot. We also observed the formation of
188 a clot in the central vortex. In contrast to FD-4.0, the inertia-driven flow jet was not slow
189 enough to promote platelet attachment. This flow pattern resulted in a heterogeneous clot with
190 a higher platelet concentration limited to the outer layers of clot initially formed in the central
191 vortex (Figure 4). These findings agreed qualitatively with the experimental observations in
192 [12] and provided support to the hypothesis that rapid formation of clot in regions of extensive
193 stasis results in a less platelet-rich clot, however, as the clot grows and interacts with the blood
194 flow, more platelets come in contact with the forming clot, which results in formation of a more
195 platelet-rich clot [19, 41].

196

197 *Coverage of the aneurysm neck.* Formation of a platelet-rich organised clot over the aneurysm
198 neck is essential to close the aneurysm and facilitate endothelialisation [17, 33]. In our sim-
199 ulations, we did not consider surface reactions on the FD struts. However, in the FD-4.5, we
200 observed the formation of a thin platelet-rich layer covering the proximal section of the aneurysm
201 neck and extending to a thicker layer in the central section of the neck. The distal section of
202 the neck remained patent. In the FD-4.0, we observed a thick platelet-rich layer covering the
203 aneurysm neck. Similar behaviour was reported in in vitro experiments [12] and also in [17, 33],
204 where the FD failed to close the sac in real aneurysms. In the FD-4.5, the clot formed in the
205 central region of the sac was surrounded by a flow jet that prevented a full coverage of the neck
206 with a stable clot. The FD-4.0 altered the flow pattern inside the sac and facilitated layer-wise
207 growth of the clot and finally the full coverage of the aneurysm neck with a platelet-rich clot.

208 4.2. Clinical utility

209 Treatment planning of flow diversion is usually based on the morphology of the aneurysm [5,
210 11]. Aside from symptomatic aneurysms, large and giant aneurysms and those with a high
211 aspect ratio or complex morphology are thought to be prone to post-FD haemorrhage [19].
212 Immediately after deployment, the efficacy of the FD is evaluated by measuring the reduction
213 of flow into the aneurysmal sac by angiographic examination. However, post-operative rupture
214 was reported in several cases with excellent immediate angiographic results after FD deployment
215 [19, 21, 36].

216 CFD-modellers have suggested different haemodynamic criteria for predicting successful oc-
217 clusion of aneurysms after flow diversion. For example, Ouared et al. [28] reported a minimum
218 reduction of 35% in the aneurysm mean velocity after flow diversion as a criterion for predicting
219 successful occlusion. Mut et al. [23] reported post-treatment velocity and shear rate of 1.31
220 cm/s and 16.35 s^{-1} , respectively, as criteria for successful aneurysm occlusion. In our simula-
221 tions, post-treatment haemodynamics in both FD-4.0 and FD-4.5 cases met the success criteria
222 suggested in the above studies. However, the two cases developed a clot with different qualities.
223 This shows that purely haemodynamic assessments cannot predict the likelihood of formation
224 of a stable clot. To comprehensively assess post-FD occlusion, it is necessary to consider the
225 potential quality of the FD-induced clot, i.e., whether flow diversion results in a stable white clot
226 or a red unorganised clot. Our model showed promise in predicting the biochemical composition

227 of clot structural components, fibrin and platelets, and thus, the likelihood of formation of a
228 fibrin and platelet-rich white thrombi after flow diversion.

229 Also there is evidence that in aneurysm treatment with FD, formation of a stable white clot
230 over the aneurysm neck and the consequent formation of neo-intimal layer and FD endothelial-
231 isation are of superior importance than FD-induction of the thrombi inside the aneurysm body
232 [17, 33]. Cebal *et al.* [8] trained a statistical model to predict the local occlusion based on local
233 haemodynamics and found poorer predictions near the aneurysm neck, when compared to other
234 regions of the flow diverted aneurysm. This magnifies the utility of models similar to the one in
235 the present work to further improve personalised assessment of aneurysm flow diversion.

236 4.3. Limitations

237 Low-shear stagnant flow is believed to be the main driver of thrombosis in flow-diverted
238 aneurysms [28, 30]. Dual anti-platelet inhibition regimens are prescribed to minimise, but not
239 eliminate, mechanical high-shear induced platelet activation in aneurysms treated with FDs [15].
240 In our experiments, we observed blood flow passing through the FD struts to have a maximum
241 shear rate of about 1000 s^{-1} which was below the shear rate level to activate the platelets (3000
242 s^{-1} [31]). Maximum shear stress near the struts was less than 15 Pa in our simulations. Accord-
243 ing to the Hellums locus of high shear-induced platelet activation [16], such shear stress levels
244 require an exposure time greater than 100 s to activate platelets. Given the near-strut maxi-
245 mum residence time in our simulations, about 1 s, mechanical activation does not likely to play a
246 significant role in our experiments. Although we did not explicitly model mechanical activation,
247 we analysed the sensitivity of our results to the background platelet activation level. In this
248 way, we were able to implicitly measure the effect of putative mechanically activated platelets
249 washing into the aneurysm sac. The reference background platelet activation was 5% in our ex-
250 periments. For the FD-4.0 case, we repeated our experiments with 1% and 10% activation levels,
251 maintaining the concentration of the resting platelets. Changing the background activation level
252 did not affect the growth pattern and locations of low/high platelet content clot formation and
253 deposition. We also performed a point-wise comparison between FiPi values throughout the
254 sac. FiPi values were $4 \pm 11\%$ lower when using 1% background platelet activation and $7 \pm 18\%$
255 higher when 10% background activation level was used. We then studied the sensitivity of the
256 platelet-rich clot morphology to the background platelet activation level. We set $\text{FiPi} > 0.15$ as
257 a threshold and extracted the platelet-rich clot morphology. High DSC scores 95.5% and 94.0%
258 were achieved when the reference clot morphology (based on 5% background activation) was
259 compared with morphologies obtained from simulations with 1% and 10% background platelet
260 activation levels, respectively.

261 The thrombosis model parameters were taken from experimental literature or relevant com-
262 putational studies that performed sensitivity analyses, except the fibrin concentration at which
263 rate of platelet attachment to the fibrin mesh is half of its maximum value, $C_{fi,50}$. A fixed value
264 of this concentration was used in all our simulations. A sensitivity analysis was performed with
265 twice and half of the original concentration, i.e., $C_{fi,50} = 60 \text{ nM}$. We observed only small effects
266 on the location and extent of the thrombus deposition, and on the distribution of platelets in the
267 final clot. DSC scores of 89.2% and 92.5% were achieved when the platelet-rich clot morphology
268 obtained with $C_{fi,50} = 60 \text{ nM}$ was compared to morphologies obtained with two times and half
269 of this value, respectively. More comprehensive analyses must determine the sensitivity of clot
270 composition and morphology to the model parameters.

271 Due to the computational burden required, the time scale of our thrombosis model is not rep-
272 resentative of the physiological time scale of FD-induced clot formation and aneurysm occlusion,

273 i.e., weeks to months. We relate this to: (i) the extensive simplification of the thrombosis chem-
274 ical network, neglecting several molecular and cellular level phenomena involved in initiation,
275 progression, and inhibition of thrombosis course after flow diversion, (ii) neglecting phenomena
276 like lysis, organisation, and contraction of the clot (iii) neglecting the effect of flow pulsation
277 on the reactions, especially on the initiation reactions when the clot-related concentrations are
278 small, and (iv) the effect of anti-coagulants and anti-platelets that are both common in flow
279 diversion patients. We did not consider such anticoagulation in our model.

280 Augsburger et al. [4] showed that flow pulsation is not a major determinant of FD perfor-
281 mance in terms of reducing aneurysmal velocity. Since we were mostly interested in the final
282 state of the clot and not in phenomena like thrombus breakdown, we did not consider flow
283 pulsatility and our simulations were performed using a non-pulsatile (steady) inflow boundary
284 condition, however, the thrombosis model can easily be run with pulsatile boundary conditions.

285 5. Conclusion

286 The thrombosis model in the present study was developed to predict the platelet content
287 distribution in intra-aneurysmal clots formed after flow diversion. The predictions made by
288 the model showed qualitative similarities in the clotting pattern and platelet composition when
289 compared with an in-vitro phantom experiment performed by an independent research group in
290 [12]. We also compared our model predictions against the literature on qualitative thrombotic
291 behaviour in aneurysms treated with flow diverters.

292 Conflict of interest statement

293 All the authors declare no conflicts of interest exist.

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